

TABLE 1—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

System	Formation constants	Temp. 25°			Ionic strength		
		0.1	0.2	0.3	0.1 35°	0.1 45°	0.0 25°
Ni ^{II} -TDAA	log K ₁	4.26	4.49	4.66	4.26	4.23	4.07
	log K ₂	2.83	2.99	3.20	2.78	2.75	2.64
Ni ^{II} -TDPA	log K ₁	3.86	3.47	3.56	3.93	3.31	3.23
Ni ^{II} -DTDAA	log K ₁	2.84	2.89	2.91	2.83	2.78	2.81
Ni ^{II} -IDAA	log K ₁	3.22	3.27	3.81	3.21	3.18	3.17
	log K ₂	6.03	6.05	6.10	5.96	5.92	6.00
Ni ^{II} -ODAA	log K ₁	2.74	2.77	2.81	2.72	2.69	2.70
Cu ^{II} -TDAA	log K ₁	4.63	4.66	4.69	4.61	4.60	4.60
	log K ₂	2.81	2.83	2.84	2.81	2.77	2.79
Cu ^{II} -TDPA	log K ₁	3.96	4.01	4.05	3.93	3.92	3.92
Cu ^{II} -IDAA	log K ₁	3.63	3.68	3.72	3.59	3.55	3.58
	log K ₂	5.80	5.88	5.94	5.78	5.76	5.73
Cu ^{II} -ODAA	log K ₁	3.95	3.99	4.03	3.93	3.89	3.91

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF Ni^{II} AND Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

System	$\mu=0.1 M$		
	$-\Delta G$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal deg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
Ni ^{II} -TDAA	9.67	2.85	22.13
Ni ^{II} -TDPA	4.58	1.34	10.51
Ni ^{II} -DTDAA	3.87	1.66	7.17
Ni ^{II} -IDAA	19.44	3.25	52.52
Ni ^{II} -ODAA	3.74	1.72	6.55
Cu ^{II} -TDAA	10.16	3.32	22.16
Cu ^{II} -TDPA	5.40	1.04	14.15
Cu ^{II} -IDAA	19.68	3.73	50.46
Cu ^{II} -ODAA	5.39	1.90	11.82

the complexes are both enthalpy and entropy stabilized. The relatively smaller values of ΔH in comparison to that of ΔS indicate that entropy is the principal driving force for the complex formation in aqueous solution.

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Studies on L-2-Aminomercaptopropionic Acid Metal Complex Equilibria

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OUT of sulphur containing amino acids, the investigation on the complexes of D-penicillamine and L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid are reported in literature¹. In this note we report our results on stepwise stability constants of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid with Be^{II}, La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Au^{III}, Zr^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI}O₂. We have evaluated thermodynamic parameters from the values obtained on stability constants using temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation².

Experimental

L-2-Aminomercaptopropionic acid (Eastern Organic Chemicals) was assayed by iodometry and by iron catalysed oxidation with oxygen and found to contain 95% SH group⁸. Throughout the investigation, standard solution of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid was stored under N₂ and discarded after 1 day. Assays of 2 days' old solutions stored under N₂ showed that the percentage of SH group lowered to 92%.

The pH-titration of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid with proton and various metal ions was conducted at 0.1 M ionic strength using KNO₃ by Bjerrum and Calvin pH titration technique as modified by Irving and Rassotti⁴⁻⁵. All the experiments were performed in N₂ atmosphere. The following reaction mixtures were prepared to study metal ion-L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid complex equilibria: (i) KNO₃ (1.0 M) 5.0 ml + HNO₃ (0.05 M) 5.0 ml, (ii) KNO₃ (1.0 M) 5.0 ml + HNO₃ (0.05 M) 5.0 ml + L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid (0.01 M) 10.0 ml, (iii) KNO₃ (1.0 M) 5.0 ml + HNO₃ (0.05 M) 5.0 ml + L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid (0.01 M) 10.0 ml + metal ion (0.01 M) 2.0 ml. The total volume of reaction mixture was raised to 50.0 ml by adding distilled water. Reaction mixture was titrated with alkali. Before titration, reaction mixtures were kept in a thermostat to attain the desired temperature.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves, it has been observed that in the lower pH range (3.0-4.5), L-2-amino-

mercaptopropionic acid shows higher values of pH as compared to acid curve. The ligand diverges from the acid curve on further addition of alkali. It has generally been observed that the complex curve overlaps with ligand in the lower pH range but diverges towards right at higher pH, indicating the release of proton due to complex formation. The formation of complex is also supported by the fact that the solutions undergo marked change in colour. Further rise in pH leads to precipitation of hydrolysed species. From the differences in the curves $\bar{n}_H$ and $\bar{n}$ were evaluated. Protonation constant values were evaluated using Bjerrum's half $\bar{n}$ method and Speakman's method⁶. The same method was applied for evaluating the stepwise stability constant of metal complexes from the $\bar{n}/pL$ data. The results obtained on stability constants and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1. The measured protonation constant of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid are in good agreement with the reported values⁷. The gradual deprotonation of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid by addition of alkali leads to the following progressive formation of metal ion:L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid complexes.

The order of stability constants of metal complexes is as follows: Au^{III} > Pt^{IV} > Th^{IV} > U^{VI}O₂ > Ce^{III} > Nd^{III} > Pr^{III} > Zr^{IV} > La^{III} > Be^{II}.

Gold(III) and platinum(IV) have very high B-class character, therefore, their complexes exhibit highest stabilities. From thorium(IV) onwards the B-class character decreases and the stability constants also decrease, the lowest stability constants being exhibited by lanthanum(III) and beryllium(II) complexes as these two metal ions have typical A-class character.

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TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT AND FREE ENERGY CHANGE VALUES OF Mⁿ⁺: L-2-AMINOMERCAPTOPROPIONIC ACID SYSTEM

Cation	Temp. 15°/(30°)			-ΔF° kcal mol ⁻¹
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β _n	
Be ^{II}	12.50 (12.35)	7.50 (7.40)	20.00 (19.75)	16.46 (17.11)
La ^{III}	13.35 (13.25)	5.90 (5.20)	18.65 (18.45)	17.58 (18.36)
Ce ^{III}	13.50 (13.40)	7.00 (6.90)	20.50 (20.80)	17.77 (18.57)
Pr ^{III}	13.40 (13.30)	5.25 (5.15)	18.65 (18.45)	17.64 (18.48)
Nd ^{III}	13.45 (13.35)	5.30 (5.20)	18.75 (18.55)	17.71 (18.50)
Au ^{III}	14.85 (14.65)	—	14.85 (14.65)	19.55 (20.30)
Pt ^{IV}	13.40 (13.35)	5.25 (5.15)	18.65 (18.50)	17.64 (18.50)
Zr ^{IV}	14.40 (13.15)	—	14.40 (14.15)	18.96 (19.61)
Th ^{IV}	14.30 (14.05)	—	14.30 (14.05)	18.83 (19.47)
U ^{VI} O ₂	13.80 (13.65)	8.70 (8.55)	22.50 (22.20)	18.17 (18.91)

Accuracy of all values are ±0.02. Protonation constant values of L-2-aminomercaptopropionic acid at 15° and 30° are log K₁^H = 10.45 (10.35); log K₂^H = 8.15 (8.10); log B^H = 18.60 (18.45), respectively.